

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_c_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 11:45:47 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	92.57	µm	
Size:	65531	digits	
Spacing:	1.413	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x...filtered (λ s 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_c_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 11:45:47 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	13.35	μm	
Min:	-8.003	μm	
Max:	5.350	μm	
Size:	94525	digits	
Spacing:	0.1413	nm	
NM-points ratio:	14.83 % (1334378 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_na...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 11:45:47 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	13.35	μm	
Size:	94525	digits	
Spacing:	0.1413	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.471	μm	
Ssk	-0.2737		
Sku	6.226		
Sp	5.152	μm	
Sv	8.202	μm	
Sz	13.35	μm	
Sa	1.084	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.6035	%	
Smc	1.717	μm	
Sxp	2.667	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	23.55	μm	
Str	*****		
Std	33.00	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.5207		
Sdr	8.532	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.1057	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.823	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.1057	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	1.087	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	1.653	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.1700	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

Warnings

Str: The autocorrelation lobe touches the edges. Try to level the...

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	9.434	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.469	µm
Mean density of furrows	4011	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	45.02	°
Second direction	180.0	°
Third direction	33.72	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	77.84	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

